

Sustainability through digital transition: the case of small cultural stakeholders

George Pavlidis, Stella Markantonatou, Chairi Kiourt, Vasileios Sevetlidis, Vasileios Arampatzakis, Helena G. Theodoropoulou, and Dimitrios Karamatskos

Athena Research Center, University Campus at Kimmeria, GR-67100 Xanthi, Greece

Abstract

It is long recognized that for cultural institutions to fulfill their goals, they need to rely on digital technologies, sustainable practices, and modern business models. The increasing number of public and private non-profit museums, although usually small, face a large volume of management needs in their efforts to attract funds for maintenance and growth, to internally manage their assets, as well as to be visible to the relevant market in order to efficiently serve their goals and ensure long-term viability.

Securing funds and running promotion campaigns for a museum are based on public relations communication policy strategies that require the creation of a feasible macro-, medium- and short-term communication program, where the current situation, the targeting, specific strategies and tactics are taken into account. At the same time, asset management has become more complicated because, on one hand, museums interact with their audience with educational programs, periodic exhibitions, etc., and on the other hand, they offer digital services, like electronic guides, virtual tours, virtual exhibitions, etc.

Recently, there has been an intense activity in the digitization and application of digital tools and services for cultural heritage, including: new added-value content through multi-dimensional digitization, documentation with standardized data schemas and metadata, advanced cultural management, standardized controlled vocabularies, virtual exhibitions and museums, advanced visualization and tools for the heritage experts, digital guides and storytelling, virtual, augmented and mixed reality, geoinformatics, gamification and innovative educational technologies. Even complex combinations of all these have already been presented, multiple times.

However, small cultural institutions face significant challenges in embracing this revolution. Their non-profit nature, limited staffing, the multitude of tasks required, and the need for technical specialization make it nearly impossible for them to join. Consequently, their work becomes more complex, putting their sustainability and viability at risk.

Project *Thalia-Digital toolset for the analysis, promotion and protection of the Greek cultural reserve in small cultural institutions* presents a unique attempt to tackle these challenges, maybe for the first time as a compact proposal of a complete framework, which includes modern and adapted asset management and marketing planning strategies, along with a state-of-the-art toolset. *Thalia* proposes a complete *Culture-Technology-Economy* framework bridged with clustering concepts in an otherwise disconnected domain. *Thalia* builds on the CIDOC-CRM data model and a shared Web structure for all tools and services. Potential user-institutions will have access to common secure and private asset management, asset valuation, communication planning, virtual world for exhibitions (Figure 1b), adapted guided tour apps, and information sources, such as crowdfunding portals. In addition, a collaborative augmented reality tool based on the Microsoft HoloLens technology brings another digital innovation by connecting multiple stakeholders in a common virtual space for event planning and asset sharing (Figure 2). The participation in *Thalia* of a significant cultural institution ensures the validity of the designed digital transition and guarantees the impact of this effort.

Acknowledgment

This research has been co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund of the European Union and Greek national funds through the Operational Program Competitiveness, Entrepreneurship and Innovation, under the call RESEARCH – CREATE – INNOVATE (project code: T2EDK-01018).

(a) A visit to a virtual museum.

(b) Two visitors in the virtual world.

Figure 1: The virtual world of Museums in Thalia.

Figure 2: Screenshot during an augmented reality collaborative exhibition design session between two parties.